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Apprenticeship and Succession Planning of Family-Owned Businesses in South-East, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined apprenticeship and succession planning of family-owned businesses in South-East, Nigeria. Descriptive survey method based on primary and secondary sources of data collection was adopted. Data was obtained from primary and secondary sources. Primary data was gathered through questionnaire while the secondary data was gathered from a review of several research publications, annual reports, articles, textbooks, unpublished thesis, journals and internet sources related family businesses. The study population consisted of 43,868 family-owned businesses. The sample size is 554 determined using Cochran (1963) statistical formula. Analyses were carried out using simple descriptive statistics organized and presented in tables, frequency and simple percentages. At the inferential level of statistical analyses, the hypothesis was subjected to double-test using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and Simple Linear Regression. To establish whether an outcome is statistically significant, the researcher set up a 5% significance level while a 95% confidence level was applied and tested at 5% ($p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$) alpha level. All analyses were carried out in SPSS 20.0.R, the correlation coefficient has a value of 0.843 which is statistically significant with $t = 38.249$. The study concludes based on the results above that there is a positive and significant relationship between apprenticeship and succession planning in a family-owned business, South-East, Nigeria. The study recommends that apprentices should be groomed, tested and held ready to succeed their masters when the need arises to save the businesses from succession crises which could lead to the death of the business.

Keywords: *Apprentice, Apprenticeship, Succession, Succession Planning and Family-Owned Businesses*

Introduction: Family-owned businesses play an important role in economic, employment, industrialisation, crime reduction, improved social life, entrepreneurial growth and development, income generation and wealth accumulation which all contribute immensely to the gross domestic product (GDP). In advanced economies, a significant percentage of their economies were and are still controlled by family dynasties such as the Rothschild, Barings, Vanderbilt, Rockefeller, Waltons, Walt Disney, Johnson and Johnson, Bill Gates Foundation and much more in the USA. In Mexico, family-owned businesses contribute to its employment generation (40%), Gross Democratic Product (40-50%), and the number of businesses (70-90 %) (Malfavón, 2012; José & Alejandra, 2016). In the United Kingdom, family businesses are a common sight such as the local newsagents, corner-shops and many independent retailers. Similarly, Japan, which controls most of the world's trade and foreign direct investment (FDI), is home to some of the oldest recorded family-controlled businesses in history such as Hoshi Ryokan (718), Toraya (1600), Enshu Sado School (1602), Takenaka Corporation (1610), Kikkoman Corporation (1630) and Sumitomo (1630). A survey carried out in Japan showed that 80 per cent of family firms had a family member CEO, three out of five firms were 100 per cent family owned and the

remaining companies were more than 50 per cent family-owned, thus making Japan significant radar in Family Business Research (NOUN, 2017).

Family-owned businesses face a lot of challenges ranging from their initiations, management and their lifespan, leading to the collapse of most of them leaving many people jobless (Nkam, et al., 2017). Thus, the main thrust of this study is to examine apprenticeship and succession planning of family-owned businesses in the South-East, Nigeria. To achieve the research objective, one research question was formulated: 'To what extent does apprenticeship benefits the succession planning in family-owned businesses?' Similarly, one hypothesis was equally formulated in line with the objective of the study and research questions. That is, the nature of ownership composition significantly affects management in family-owned businesses.

Literature Review: The concept and subject of succession planning in family-owned business is not the type easily yield to a one-fit-all definition. Nonetheless, Zahrani, Nikmaram and Latift (2014) state that the succession planning process in family businesses is recognized as one of the most important phases of the family business lifecycle. The authors among other researchers believe that the most important issue in managing the family business is a successor-planning process that rarely happens in family businesses. Successor planning in family businesses is finding a successor who is both interested in joining the family business and has the capability and capacity of managing a family business. Carol (2004) cited in Christie (2005) and Zahrani *et al*, (2014) defines successor planning as a systematic process by which personal and professional breeding are combined and one can achieve this confidence that organization is ready to fill any vacancy by right people with right skills and insights, and at the right time. Such definition involves all skills, knowledge, attitudes, and behaviours that are necessary for performing various roles. This definition involves all skills, knowledge, attitudes, and behaviours that are necessary for performing various roles (Christie, 2005; Zahrani *et al*, 2014). The most important advantage of succession planning is that it facilitates human resource effective planning and by using it, the right people inside the organization fill the right job at the right time to achieve business goals. The essence of a successor planning process is to identify, train, and develop the people who can acquire key jobs by possessing necessary knowledge and skills (Taylor & McGraw, 2004; Zahrani *et al*, 2014).

Rules for Successor Planning Success

Conger and Fulmer (2003) cited in Zahrani *et al*, (2014) provided five rules for successor planning success.

- i. Focus on developmental activities whose aim is to prepare successor candidates via in-service training and such activities as authorization to acquire target jobs.
- ii. Focus on key jobs necessary for organizational long-term health.
- iii. Reveal the system as clearly as possible and avoid the ambiguities and the people should be informed of their situation in any moment. In such a system, procedures and laws are transferred to all organizational members.
- iv. There should be continuous measurement of progress and avoid successor planning traditional mindset.
- v. Keep the system flexible so that system designers can remove its deficiencies and improve it continuously based on implementers' feedback.

Attributes of Apprenticeship among Family-Owned Businesses in South-East, Nigeria

i. Contractual Standing: Family business owners undertake the training function of apprentice under a written or oral agreement with or without a clause to retain the apprentice at the expiration or successful graduation of the apprentice. The apprenticeship contract is clearly different from the employment contract, with the apprenticeship contract spelling out formally the training-related rights and duties of the apprentice and the employer, while the employment contract does the same for the service-related rights and duties of the employee and the employer; and, second, that apprentices should hold a training contract only.

ii. The Right to Strike: An apprentice does not have the right to strike. He/she is considered more or less a member of the family of his master as well as the business. Thus, apprentices' rights to participate in industrial

disputes is treated as a case that can attract severe sanction, punishment, suspension, expulsion from the business or even outright cancellation or termination of his contract of apprenticeship. The right to strike is not allowed in family business and it could affect not just the operation and profitability of the business but as well threaten its sustainability.

iii. The Right to Public Holiday: The right to public holiday to apprentices remains a debate among family business owners. Businesses whether family or non-family business are known to have ignored public holiday declaration by the government. So, in a family-owned business, apprentices' holiday's request is granted on the account ill-health by the apprentice or any of his/her immediate family members that require closer attention or visitation by the apprentice. Other occasions are strictly determined by the manager or business owner. An apprentice observance of the holiday without the consent of his master is viewed as a mark of disobedience that would attract punishment or sanction.

iv. The Right to Payment of Allowance, Remuneration and Lump-Sum: The right to payment of allowance, remuneration and lump-sum is available for apprenticeship depending on the content or preference of the apprentice. An apprentice wishing to remain in the business after training enjoys all of the above. However, those wishing to learn the trade and its techniques may not enjoy any of the above because he/she is seen as a formal apprentice with on interest in developing and acquiring new skills. There are however occasions where apprenticeship is contracted on the basis that the apprentice will be given a lump-sum at the successful graduation to start his/her business. This case is particularly the case with so many entrepreneurs in South-East, Nigeria. The lump-sum enables apprenticeship graduate to start their own business.

v. The Right to Welfare and Adequate Care: Right to welfare and adequate care are important rights enjoyed by apprentices under their masters especially those who have chosen remain with their masters in the business after training. However, other categories of apprentices also enjoy these rights but not as much as those that will be retained. The family business owner takes care of their health, emotional, proper moral and religious wellbeing to ensure that upon graduation; they will become useful to themselves, their families, community and the society in general.

Succession Planning and Family-Owned Business

Succession in family firms is a problem in all firms. However, succession in the family business has been found to be different from non-family business in important ways. In particular, research on executive succession in non-family firms has shown that the process often involves a period of adjustment in which the successor seeks to undermine the predecessor in order to augment her or his own legitimacy and to establish a clean break from the past (Ashcraft, 1999; Gephart, 1991; Dalpiaz, Tracey & Phillips, 2014). Succession planning thus is a dynamic process requiring the current ownership to plan the company's future with many involved parties. It means making the preparations to facilitate the transfer process and to ensure the harmony of the family, the harmony between the family and non-family constituents, the continuity of the enterprise, and fulfilment of the future needs of both the family and the business (Landsberg, 1988; Dunn, 1999; Sharma et al., 2003a). It is also interaction among several factors operating at the personal, relational, and organisational levels (e.g. the personal and career development of the successor, succession planning, and control activities) (Tatoglu et al., 2008).

Succession planning has been proved to be one of the most important factors determining the continuity of a firm from one generation to the next. The overlap between the activities considered by the researcher to be components of the succession process, and between activities considered to be parts of succession planning, is significant (Sharma et al., 2003a). Succession planning itself also increases cooperation and communication between different stakeholders (Sharma et al. 2003b). Still, leadership transfer is seldom planned in a family business (Landsberg, 1988; Handler, 1990; Sharma et al., 2003a; Westhead, 2003). Researchers have found several factors positively influencing the extent of succession planning. Davis and Harveston (1998) represent a process model of succession planning with four levels of analysis: individual-level characteristics (e.g. owner manager's age and education), group-level influence (e.g. family members participating in the day-to-day operations), organizational-level attributes (e.g. size, formality), and resources (e.g. family funding). When

testing the model empirically, they found that developing an extensive succession planning process rests mostly in the hands of those family members who are involved in the day-to-day operations across all generations. In addition, they found empirical evidence about the moderate effect of the generation on succession planning. Although each of the four levels was found to be significant among first-generation family firms in explaining the extensiveness of the succession planning process, the number of factors found to be significant declined with each succeeding generation (Davis & Harveston, 1998). If the incumbent is insecure about the ability of a potential successor to fulfil expectations, or about a successor's trustworthiness, they are less likely to pursue succession and succession planning (Sharma et al. 2003a).

Successors in family firms need to construct a vision of the future that is consistent with, and generally complementary to, the legacy of previous generations of family leaders (Poza & Messer, 2001; Dalpiaz, et al., 2014). As a result, family business succession is a complex and often lengthy process that involves "the actions, events and developments that affect the transfer of managerial control" among family members (De Massis et al., 2008; Dalpiaz, et al., 2014). Most family businesses do not compete with external candidates for their roles and positions and some authors believe that because family business leaders do not generally compete with external candidates for their positions, there may be a presumption of nepotism and a sense among the firm's non-family members that the successor has not been appointed on merit. This is despite evidence that nepotism may have clear economic advantages because of the knowledge and cultural synergies that exist within families (Bellow, 2004; Lee, Lim, & Lim, 2003; Dalpiaz, et al., 2014). The upshot is that in matters of succession, a challenge for family businesses is to avoid the dangers of nepotism while attempting to capitalise on its potential advantages (Steier & Miller, 2010; Dalpiaz, et al., 2014). Perhaps because of these distinctive and interesting challenges, succession is one of the most important topics in family business studies (Dalpiaz, et al., 2014).

Challenges of Succession in Family-Owned Business

The succession process brings together family expectations, the individual successor's expectations, and those of the business. As a consequence, there is often a conflict between these varying expectations (Neubauer, 2003). Besides expectations, characteristics of the key players also produce challenges to the succession. Intergenerational succession creates a large age and experience gap between old and new CEOs (Miller et al. 2003; Cabrera-Suárez, 2005). Miller et al. (2003) summarise this by suggesting that problems in intergenerational succession are mainly caused by an inappropriate relationship between past and future.

In (small) family firms, challenges in succession often arise from the smaller pool of talent from which to draw a successor (Chittoor & Das, 2007), emotional factors in the incumbent successor relationship, complex social ties with the family involved in the business (Le Breton- Miller et al. 2004), and a lack of consensus on the timing. A succession is also a rare event in a family business, so there is no experience or knowledge in the company about handling the situation. Many times, major conflicts arise over the direction of the business itself and because of the differing interests of owners, such as whether to keep or sell the business (Bararch & Ganitsky, 1995; Fox et al., 1996). A poor situation in the market environment or problems in the firm's operative management (e.g. if the product or service range no longer meets the market requirements, or if there is an outdated management style or organisation structure) may also predict problems within the succession process (Westhead, 2003, Neubauer, 2003).

The role of the incumbent in the success of the business is significant, so it is not surprising that quite many problems experienced during the succession process are also related to the incumbent (Beckhard & Dyer, 1983; Sharma et al. 2003a). Incumbents have difficulties contemplating succession for several reasons. They may fear the loss of power or legitimation to participate in the day-to-day operational decision-making and loss of status in the business, but also within the family. Succession planning forces the incumbent to face their own mortality (Landsberg, 1988; Davis & Harveston, 1998). Incumbents may also fear the loss of an important part of their identity (Landsberg, 1988; Handler, 1994; Fox et al., 1996; Davis & Harveston, 1998).

The reluctance may manifest in many ways, for example, as a reluctance to delegate power or as an ambivalence towards succession planning (Landsberg, 1988). The incumbent's reluctance to delegate power

may frustrate the learning process of the successor and decrease the successor's motivation towards the succession process. It can also reduce their credibility in the eyes of employees and other key stakeholders (Fox et al., 1996; Griffeth et al. 2006). The incumbent's resistance towards the succession can also be represented as a poor choice of a successor (Handler 1994) or tries to perpetuate the organisation's future leader in their own image (Handler, 1994). A lack of support from the incumbent to the successor may also be one example of self-defeating behaviour as a response to opposing feelings towards succession (Landsberg, 1988). The founder (and probably the incumbent of further generations) is not alone in resisting the planning process, but the family, the managers, the owners, and the environment outside the firm may also have reasons to resist the change and succession planning as a route to the change. The simultaneous changes in family life interfere with the family's ability and willingness to engage in an open discussion of succession issues (Landsberg, 1988; Barnes & Hershon, 1989). In addition, the power imbalance, family conflicts, and the lack of a successor, as well as the factors relating to organisational culture, structure, and stability, complicate the succession process (Handler, 1994).

Succession Planning and Management of Family-Owned Business

Succession planning is the deliberate and formal process that facilitates the transfer of management control from one family member to another (Sharma, Chrisma, Pablo & Chua, 2003; Tanzwani, 2010). Succession is a process during which a business is transferred from one generation to the next which involves planning, selection and preparation of the next generation of the owners or managers and the transition of the management or ownership responsibility (Van der Merwe & Ellis, 2007; Tanzwani, 2010). Succession, in a nutshell, is the process during which the business (family) is transferred from one generation to the next, while it can also be defined as transfer of management control from one family member to another, or the passing of the leadership baton from the founder/owner to a successor, who would be either a family member or a non-family member (Maas *et al.*, 2005; Tanzwani, 2010). Thus, a good and proper succession plan enhances the survival of the family-owned business. Succession is a life-long process that encompasses everything aimed at ensuring the continuity of the business through the generations, succession planning process includes all the actions, events, and the organisational mechanism by which leadership of the business and ownership is transferred (Aronoff & Ward, 1992; Tanzwani, 2010).

Each family business encounters pitfalls within the succession planning as the successor identified might not be the suitable successor for the long-term survival of the family business (Ciuffo, 2004; Tanzwani, 2010). For the family business to have a smooth succession, there must be a leader who is willing and able to hand over the leadership role to the successor, and a successor who is willing and able to take over the role through following a designed family business mechanism for such transition to take place. It is vital that both the successor and the leader be willing to enter into such a succession process, the successor must also be in good position to take the business forward to the next generation, failure by the successor to do so, will result in the death of the family business (Sharma *et al.*, 2001; Tanzwani, 2010). There must be engagement and cooperation of the family, non-family members and management team in the family business in order to ensure that the succession planning is executed successfully (Van der Merwe & Ellis, 2007; Tanzwani, 2010).

One of the most significant factors determining the continuity prospect of the family business from one generation to the next is whether the succession process is properly planned (Neubauer & Lank, 1998; Tanzwani, 2010). Many entrepreneurs dislike formal succession planning (Arnoff & Ward, 1995). Formal succession planning enhances the probability that the smooth transfer from one generation to the next can be achieved in the best interest of the family as well as the business, the easier and more successful the transition, the better the chances of survival and the long-term profitability (Maas *et al.*, 2005; Ibrahim & Ellis, 2004). Well-considered and planned succession maximises the chance of finding a competent successor which result in the smooth transition of leadership between the generations (Venter, 2003). Succession should not be seen as an event that occurs as a result of the sudden death of the founder, instead, effective succession is the result of proper planning and is an intricate process requiring a sequence of steps that should be initiated early in the

potential successor's life to prepare him or her for the leadership (Ibrahim, Soufani & Lam, 2001). It is estimated that approximately half of all the family-owned businesses fail to make it to the next generation owing to inefficient succession. It is, therefore, critical to review succession planning with the view to establish and assist the family-owned businesses with the factors that need to be considered (Ward, 2004).

Family firms seem to struggle to cope with succession, as they lack clear mechanisms and guidelines to handle the succession process (Ibrahim, Soufani & Lam, 2001; Kohr, et al., 2016). Succession planning in family firms is a critical aspect to ensure the longevity of the firm and ensure successful operation across generations. The transition of management in a firm is a very sensitive stage of the business. Transitions ideally happen gradually, but this still depends on the knowledge and ideas brought forward by the new generation. The succeeding generation can have, in fact, a very different approach to the way the business needs to be run and managed both in the short and long term. For this reason, succession will alter the perception of familiness within and outside the firm (Habbershon & Williams, 1999; Kohr, et al., 2016). One important aspect from a market-oriented point of view is the management of the identity of the family firm during the succession process. The internalisation and reflection of the current identity help to assess, manage and preserve a firm's unique families, which is considered a crucial part that has to be approached during the process of succession. It is argued that organisational knowledge is the key to success in any business (Cabrera-Suárez et al., 2001; Kohr, et al., 2016). Looking at family businesses, relationships in the firm help to enable transfer of knowledge during a succession more effectively compared to a non-family company (Bjuggren & Sund, 2002; Kohr, et al., 2016). Relationships between successor and predecessor are not limited to work and enable exchange beyond aspects related to the business. Also knowing the family business from early childhood on and dealing with the business also as a part of the family life may give a head start when entering the business (de Vries, 1994; Boyd & Royer, 2012; Kohr, et al., 2016).

Empirical Review:

A study conducted by Musa and Semasinghe (2014) examined the problem of succession among small family businesses in Nigeria. Drawing from eight small family businesses in Gombe metropolis, Gombe State of Nigeria, they examined why those businesses failed after the death of their founders. Primary data was gathered from former employees of the businesses investigated and the children as well as the relatives of the founders which was qualitatively analysed. The study also discussed some of the factors that prevented smooth succession or continuity of small businesses in Nigeria. The study found that lack of proper planning by the founders for succession is the backbone of this problem. This happens due to the fear of losing control of the business to subordinate or any of the family members by the founders. Experts believe the best time to conduct succession planning in a small business is when the business owner is between the ages of 55 and 65. In addition, there is an inheritance problem among the members of the founder's family which tie down the business. The study recommends that SFB founders should have a long-term succession management strategy by training a member of the family or hiring an expert to manage the business. Alternatively, they should sell some shares of the business to the public or a partner. Ogundele, Idris, and Ahmed-Ogundipe, (2012) on their own focused on entrepreneurial succession problems in Nigeria given the fact that many promising family businesses have collapsed over the years soon after the demise/exit of their founders. Using secondary data, the study sought to explore the issues involved in succession problems, the sources of the problems and how these have threatened the perpetuity principle in companies with respect to family businesses in Nigeria. The study found that the succession laws of Nigeria (which includes the native laws and customs) and the multi-cultural nature of Nigeria creates a myriad of succession problems for family-owned businesses in Nigeria. The study recommends the crafting of a comprehensive, well thought-out, market-focused and people-centred entrepreneurial succession planning be started early enough in the life of the business.

In another related study, Adedayo, Olanipekun and Ojo (2016) investigated the factors that are responsible for ensuring planning for succession and firm's sustainability of family businesses in Lagos and Ogun States of Nigeria. The study adopted a survey design with a population of study limited to the family business owners

who are members of the National Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (NASME). Family owned businesses in NASME from Ogun and Lagos states were 7,690 members. Total registered members on a roll of NASME (National Association of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises) as at December 2015 was 25,000 members. According to (Akande and Ojikutu, 2008), Lagos and Ogun States accounted for 60% of the business and industrial transactions in Nigeria. Therefore, Lagos and Ogun States member companies in NASME are 15,000. Members of NASME that are Family Owned Businesses (as at December 2015) in Ogun and Lagos states were 7,690 companies. The sample size of the study was determined by using Taro Yamane, 1968 ($n = N/1+N(e)^2$). The sample size of 327 firms used for this study was derived from this method, 10 CEOs were also randomly selected to participate in the qualitative in-depth interview with the 327 companies. The choice of the 10 CEOs for the in-depth interview was in line with previous research that puts the success rate between 2-5% of the sample size (Frankfort-Nachmias and Nachmias, 1996). The sampling frame consisted of the family business in Lagos and Ogun States that are members of NASME and the figure was 7,690 members. A stratified sampling technique was used to select the family businesses, from where a random sample of 327 was selected. The total of 350 questionnaires was administered, 338 were collected which represented 96.5% of the total questionnaires sent out. Of this value, 11 were invalidated leaving 327 as the valid questionnaires used for analysis. This represents 93.4% of the total questionnaires administered. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation and Multiple Regression were used to analyse the data. The study found that there was a strong positive correlation between planning for succession and firm's sustainability, with an r value of correlation coefficient at 0.93 and a significant level of $P < 0.05$ at 0.000. The study concluded that family business owners need to understand that their valued family business may not survive the next generation if they do not get serious about succession planning. The study recommends that founder must act proactively by crafting succession plan early enough in the life of the business, such that his experience will help the firm's survival and issues that can create conflicts should be avoided like appointing an incompetent successor, while the successor should be made to come into the family business early enough to gain the confidence and respect of other family and non-family workers.

Similarly, Ogbechie and Anetor (2015) assessed succession planning in a family-owned business in Lagos, Nigeria with the aim of identifying the factors preventing smooth succession in family-owned enterprises. The population of the study includes all family-owned enterprises in Lagos state, Nigeria. The study was conducted in Lagos due to the problem of unorganised association of family-owned enterprises in Nigeria and the lack of access to information. This study adopted a purposive sampling technique to select 80 participants (owners/founders of family businesses) from the population. A total of 20 usable questionnaires were completed and returned, providing a final return rate of 25%. The sample covered family-owned businesses that cut across different industries such as manufacturing, commercial, construction, and service. It is important to mention that certain criteria were used in selecting the participating family-owned businesses for this study. These criteria include family firms: existing for over three years; run by the family member (s), and evidence to pass the business on to the next generation. The study used primary data, which were collected through the administration of questionnaires to founders/owners of family-owned enterprises in Lagos. The questionnaires consist of a combination of both closed-ended and open-ended questions. A Seven-Point Likert Scale, which ranges from strongly disagree and strongly agree, was used to rate the responses from respondents. The data analyses techniques employed in this study include descriptive and factor analysis. The study used descriptive analysis to summarise the profile of participants. Factor analysis was equally employed to reduce the data and choose those items that actually measured the constructs in this study and analyses of the responses were done through the use of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The study found that the lack of a succession plan is not the significant factor responsible for the problem of succession despite the fact that most family enterprises lack a succession plan. The study concludes that there are other factors responsible for the problem of poor succession in family-owned businesses in Nigeria. The study recommends more empirical studies be conducted as regards the issue of succession in the family-owned firm in Nigeria in order to bring to bear other factors inhibiting succession.

Methodology

The design adopted for this study is a descriptive survey method based on primary and secondary sources of data collection. The data for this study was obtained from primary sources otherwise known as field survey and secondary sources otherwise called desk survey. Primary data was gathered through a structured questionnaire. The objective was to gather related, rich, detailed and specific information used in the analyses and to confirm, corroborate, dispute, reject or establish new facts or truth. The secondary data was gathered from a review of several research publications, annual reports, articles, textbooks, unpublished thesis, journals and internet sources related to organization structure and family businesses. The study population consist of registered and unregistered family-owned businesses in Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and the Imo States. A pilot study conducted by the researcher indicates there are about 43,868 family-owned businesses in the South-East. Cochran (1963) statistical formula was used to determine the sample size that gives 554. To ensure that the sample size determined above truly represent each State, a stratified random sampling technique was adopted using Bowley's proportional allocation statistical technique. The survey instrument was developed on the basis of information required to examine the research objectives of the study and composed of structured questionnaire divided into two parts namely Part A and Part B. Part A provides general information about the respondents while Part B focuses on the research questions broken into item questions to elicit responses from the respondents about their businesses. Likert scale grading format was used in designing the questionnaire. To ascertain the validity of the research instrument, the researcher subjected the instrument to face, construct, contents and response validations. To test the reliability of the research instrument, a pilot study was carried out to ensure that the items in the questionnaire were stated in clear terms without ambiguity with the same meaning to all the respondents. In order to measure internal consistency, Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient (r) was used to test the reliability of responses by the 25 respondents. The result shows that the Cronbach's Alpha of $0.84 > 0.70$ was achieved. This implies that the reliability of the test instrument was very high and reliable too. The study analyses made using simple descriptive statistics organized and presented in tables, frequency and simple percentages to calculate, analyse, show and summarize the responses of the respondents and the research question in a meaningful way. At the inferential level of statistical analyses, the hypothesis was subjected to double-test using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and Simple Linear Regression to determine their statistical significance or otherwise. To establish whether an outcome is statistically significant, the researcher set up a 5% significance level. This implies that the researcher accepted a statistical significance occurring 5 times out of 100 (5/100) by chance. Thus, a 95% confidence level was applied and tested at 5% (p -value ≤ 0.05) alpha level. The maximum acceptable risk of making type 1 error (rejecting the null hypotheses (H_0) when it should have been accepted) is 5%. Hence, the decision rule adopted in this study is to reject the null hypotheses where the calculated p -value at 5% significance level with the respective degrees of freedom is greater than the critical or table value, otherwise, the null hypotheses should be accepted. However, using the probability value (p -value) produced from the SPSS software, the decision rule was to reject the null hypotheses if the probability value was less than the chosen 5% alpha level otherwise, accepted.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Administration and Return of Questionnaire: A total of five hundred and fifty-four (554) questionnaire was printed and distributed to the respondents by the researcher. The breakdown shows that five hundred and thirty-six (536) representing a response rate of 96.8% were returned while eighteen (18) questionnaire representing a non-response rate of 3.2% were not returned (see table 4.1 in the appendix). The table 4.2 in the appendix shows a total of one hundred and forty-four (144) questionnaire distributed to respondents in Abia State, South-East, Nigeria. A look at the table shows that one hundred and thirty-eight (138) questionnaire were returned out of one hundred and forty-four (144) distributed. This represents a 96.7% response rate. It further shows that one hundred and thirty-seven (137) were adjudged good for analyses representing 95.1%, one questionnaire was not properly filled representing 0.7% while six (6) questionnaire was not returned representing 4.2%. Similarly, table 4.3 in the appendix shows that a total of one hundred and thirty (130) questionnaire were distributed to respondents in Anambra State, South-East, Nigeria. A look at the table shows that one hundred and twenty-

seven (127) questionnaire were returned out of one hundred and thirty (130) distributed. This represents a 98.6% response rate. A further breakdown shows that one hundred and twenty-six (126) were adjudged good for analyses representing 96.9%, one questionnaire was not properly filled representing 0.8% while two (2) questionnaire was not returned representing 2.3%.

In Ebonyi State, South-East, Nigeria, table 4.4 in the appendix shows that a total of ninety-four (94) questionnaire was distributed to respondents. A look at the table reveals that all the ninety-four (94) questionnaire distributed were returned. This represents 100.0% response rate. A further breakdown shows that ninety-three (93) was adjudged good for analyses representing 98.9% and one questionnaire was not properly filled representing 1.1%. Meanwhile, in Enugu State, South-East, Nigeria, table 4.5 shows that a total of eighty-five (85) questionnaire was distributed to respondents. The table equally shows that eighty-four (84) out of eighty-five (85) questionnaire distributed were returned. This represents a 99.0% response rate. A further breakdown shows that eighty-three (83) were adjudged good for analyses representing 97.6%, one questionnaire was not properly filled representing 1.2% and one questionnaire was not properly filled representing 1.2% respectively. Table 4.6 in the appendix shows that a total of one hundred and one (101) questionnaire were distributed to respondents in Imo State, South-East, Nigeria. The table also shows that the ninety-nine (99) questionnaire distributed were returned. This represents a 98.0% response rate. A further breakdown shows that ninety-seven (97) was adjudged good for analyses representing 96.0% and two questionnaires were not properly filled representing 2.0% while another two were not returned representing 2.0% respectively.

Analyses of Responses in the Research Objective

To what extent does apprenticeship affect the succession planning in family-owned businesses?

Coded responses on To what extent does apprenticeship benefits the succession planning in family-owned businesses?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Apprenticeship in the family business is undertaken as a strategy to ensure smooth leadership succession	533	3.728	.9435
Succession planning in family-owned businesses is based on the informal education, training and development of the future managers on the business	533	4.488	.6733
succession planning in most family-owned businesses is an effort at finding and breeding right people with skills, knowledge, attitudes, experience and behaviours within the family circle that can lead in the business	533	4.276	.9718
Only successful apprentices are considered during leadership succession in family-owned businesses	533	3.869	.9526
Apprenticeship does not benefit succession planning in family-owned businesses	533	1.992	1.0130
Valid N (listwise)	533		

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version

The table 4.7 above shows the mean score of each item questions in the research question five. A calculation of the all the mean shows a grand total of 18.353 in all. A further breakdown shows a grand mean score of 3.6706. Thus, given that the acceptance point is 3.0, the grand mean value of 3.4 as calculated from the descriptive table above indicate that apprenticeship significantly benefits succession planning in family-owned businesses in the South-East, Nigeria.

Table 2: Apprenticeship in the family business is undertaken as a strategy to ensure smooth leadership succession

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	5	.9	.9	.9
Disagree	48	9.0	9.0	9.9
Undecided	155	29.1	29.1	39.0
Agree	204	38.3	38.3	77.3

Strongly Agree	121	22.7	22.7	100.0
Total	533	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 4.8 above present results of responses of item question one in research question five that seeks to examine the extent to which apprenticeship benefits the succession planning in family-owned businesses. The result of the analyses based on the responses of the respondents shows a response frequency of five hundred and thirty-three (533). The observed response rate of strongly disagree is five (5) representing 0.9%, forty-eight (48) respondents of disagreeing represent 9.0% and one hundred and fifty-five (155) of undecided representing 29.1%. However, two hundred and four (204) respondents agree to represent 38.3% and one hundred and twenty-one (121) respondents strongly agree to represent 22.7%. This implies that 9.9% of the respondents disagree/strongly disagree that apprenticeship in the family business is undertaken as a strategy to ensure smooth leadership succession. Similarly, 61.0% of the respondents agree/strongly agree that apprenticeship in the family business is undertaken as a strategy to ensure smooth leadership succession while 29.1% were indifferent. Therefore, given that the acceptance point is 3.0, the grand mean value of 3.728 as shown in the descriptive table presented above indicates that apprenticeship in the family business is undertaken as a strategy to ensure smooth leadership succession.

Table 3: Succession planning in family-owned businesses is based on the informal education, training and development of the future managers on the business

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	2	.4	.4	.4
Disagree	9	1.7	1.7	2.1
Undecided	15	2.8	2.8	4.9
Agree	208	39.0	39.0	43.9
Strongly Agree	299	56.1	56.1	100.0
Total	533	100.0	100.0	

Source: Data Analyses in IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 4.9 above present results of responses of item question two in research question five that seeks to examine the extent to which apprenticeship benefits the succession planning in family-owned businesses. The result of the analyses based on the responses of the respondents shows a response frequency of five hundred and thirty-three (533). The observed response rate of strongly disagree is two (2) representing 0.4%, nine (9) respondents of disagreeing represent 1.7% and fifteen (15) of undecided representing 2.8%. However, two hundred and eight (208) respondents agree to represent 39.0% and two hundred and ninety-nine (299) respondents strongly agree to represent 56.1%. This implies that 2.1% of the respondents disagree/strongly disagree that succession planning in family-owned businesses is based on the informal education, training and development of the future managers on the business. Similarly, 95.1% of the respondents agree/strongly agree that succession planning in family-owned businesses is based on the informal education, training and development of the future managers on the business while 2.8% were indifferent. Therefore, given that the acceptance point is 3.0, the grand mean value of 4.488 as shown in the descriptive table presented above indicates that succession planning in family-owned businesses is based on the informal education, training and development of the future managers on the business.

Table 4: Succession planning in most family-owned businesses is an effort at finding and breeding right people with skills, knowledge, attitudes, experience and behaviours within the family circle that can lead in the business

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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Valid	Strongly Disagree	17	3.2	3.2	3.2
	Disagree	31	5.8	5.8	9.0
	Undecided	3	.6	.6	9.6
	Agree	219	41.1	41.1	50.7
	Strongly Agree	263	49.3	49.3	100.0
	Total	533	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 4.10 above present results of responses of item question three in research question five that seeks to examine the extent to which apprenticeship benefits the succession planning in family-owned businesses. The result of the analyses based on the responses of the respondents shows a response frequency of five hundred and thirty-three (533). The observed response rate of strongly disagree is seventeen (17) representing 3.2%, thirty-one (31) respondents of disagreeing represent 5.8% and three (3) of undecided representing 0.6%. Meanwhile, two hundred and nineteen (219) respondents agree to represent 41.1% and two hundred and sixty-three (263) respondents strongly agree to represent 49.3%. This implies that 9.0% of the respondents disagree/strongly disagree that succession planning in most family-owned businesses is an effort at finding and breeding right people with skills, knowledge, attitudes, experience and behaviours within the family circle that can lead in the business. Similarly, 90.4% of the respondents agree/strongly agree that succession planning in most family-owned businesses is an effort at finding and breeding right people with skills, knowledge, attitudes, experience and behaviours within the family circle that can lead in the business while 0.6% were indifferent. Therefore, given that the acceptance point is 3.0, the grand mean value of 4.276 as shown in the descriptive table presented earlier indicates that succession planning in most family-owned businesses is an effort at finding and breeding right people with skills, knowledge, attitudes, experience and behaviours within the family circle that can lead in the business.

Table 5: Only successful apprentices are considered during leadership succession in family-owned businesses

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	4	.8	.8
	Disagree	38	7.1	7.9
	Undecided	143	26.8	34.7
	Agree	187	35.1	69.8
	Strongly Agree	161	30.2	100.0
	Total	533	100.0	100.0

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 4.11 above present results of responses of item question four in research question five that seeks to examine the extent to which apprenticeship benefits the succession planning in family-owned businesses. The result of the analyses based on the responses of the respondents shows a response frequency of five hundred and thirty-three (533). The observed response rate of strongly disagree is four (4) representing 0.8%, thirty-eight (38) respondents of disagreeing represent 7.1% and one hundred and forty-three (143) of undecided representing 26.8%. Meanwhile, one hundred and eighty-seven (187) respondents agree to represent 35.1% and one hundred and sixty-one (161) respondents strongly agree to represent 30.2%. This implies that 7.9% of the respondents disagree/strongly disagree that only successful apprentices are considered during leadership succession in family-owned businesses. Similarly, 65.3% of the respondents agree/strongly agree that only successful apprentices are considered during leadership succession in family-owned businesses while 26.8% were indifferent. Therefore, given that the acceptance point is 3.0, the grand mean value of 3.869 as shown in the descriptive table presented earlier indicates that only successful apprentices are considered during leadership succession in family-owned businesses.

Table 6: Apprenticeship does not benefit succession planning in family-owned businesses

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	217	40.7	40.7
	Disagree	156	29.3	70.0
	Undecided	112	21.0	91.0
	Agree	43	8.1	99.1
	Strongly Agree	5	.9	100.0
	Total	533	100.0	100.0

Source: Data Analyses in IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 4.12 above present results of responses of item question five in research question five that seeks to examine the extent to which apprenticeship benefits the succession planning in family-owned businesses. The result of the analyses based on the responses of the respondents shows a response frequency of five hundred and thirty-three (533). The observed response rate of strongly disagree is two hundred and seventeen (217) representing 40.7%, one hundred and fifty-six (156) respondents of disagreeing represent 29.3% and one hundred and twelve (112) of undecided representing 21.0%. Meanwhile, forty-three (43) respondents agree to represent 8.1% and five (5) respondents strongly agree to represent 0.9%. This implies that 70.0% of the respondents disagree/strongly disagree that apprenticeship does not benefit succession planning in family-owned businesses. Similarly, 9.0% of the respondents agree/strongly agree that apprenticeship does not benefit succession planning in family-owned businesses while 21.0% were indifferent. Thus, given that the acceptance point is 3.0, the grand mean value of 1.992 as shown in the descriptive table presented earlier indicates that respondents reject the view that apprenticeship does not benefit succession planning in family-owned businesses. In other words, apprenticeship benefits succession planning in family-owned businesses.

Test of Hypothesis

H₀: Apprenticeship does not benefit succession planning in a family-owned business

H₁: Apprenticeship positively and significantly benefits succession planning in the family-owned business

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Apprenticeship in family-owned businesses	3.728	.9435	533
Succession planning in family-owned businesses	4.495	.6449	533

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 8: Correlations

		Apprenticeship in family-owned businesses	Succession planning in family-owned businesses
Apprenticeship in family-owned businesses	Pearson Correlation	1	.843**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	533	533
Succession planning in family-owned businesses	Pearson Correlation	.843**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	533	533

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 9: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.843 ^a	.710	.710	.3473	.710	1302.769	1	531	.000	.068

a. Predictors: (Constant), Apprenticeship in family-owned businesses

b. Dependent Variable: Succession planning in family-owned businesses

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 10: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	157.175	1	157.175	1302.769	.000 ^b
	Residual	64.063	531	.121		
	Total	221.238	532			

a. Dependent Variable: Succession planning in family-owned businesses

b. Predictors: (Constant), Apprenticeship in family-owned businesses

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 11: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
	Apprenticeship in family-owned businesses	.576	.016	.843	36.094	.000	.545	.607

a. Dependent Variable: Succession planning in family-owned businesses

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

R = 0.843

R² = 0.710

F = 1302.769

T = 38.249

DW = 0.068

Interpretation and Decision: Table 13 shows the descriptive statistics of the relationship between apprenticeship and succession with a mean score of 3.728 and standard deviation of .9435. Succession planning has a mean score of 4.495 and a standard deviation of 0.6449. A careful observation of the standard deviation values reveals that both have almost the same variability of data points amongst the dependent and the independent variables which implies that apprenticeship positively and significantly benefits succession planning in family-owned businesses, South-East, Nigeria. Table 16 shows the regression sum of squares (157.175) is greater than the residual sum of squares (64.063) which indicate that more of the variation in the dependent variable is not explained by the model. The significance value of the F statistic (0.00) is less than 0.05 which means that the variation explained by the model is not due to chance. R, the correlation coefficient in table 4.3.5c which has a value of 0.843 indicate that there is a positive relationship between apprenticeship and succession planning in family-owned businesses in the South-East, Nigeria. R square, the coefficient of determination shows that 71.0% of the variation in the succession planning of family-owned businesses is explained by the model. With the linear regression model, the error of estimate in table 4.3.5c with a value of 0.3473 is low. The Durbin Watson statistic of 0.068 which is less than 2 indicates that there is no autocorrelation. The effect of apprenticeship and succession planning in the family-owned businesses coefficient of 0.843 indicates a significant and positive relationship between apprenticeship and succession planning which is statistically significant in table 4.3.5e with t = 38.249. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted. Hence, we conclude based on the results above that

apprenticeship positively and significantly benefits succession planning in a family-owned business, South-East, Nigeria.

Discussion of Results

The objective of the study was to appraise the effect of apprenticeship on the succession planning of family-owned businesses. The result of the analyses of research question as earlier presented revealed that apprenticeship had a significant effect on the succession planning of family-owned businesses. The computed mean of the observed responses was 3.7 higher than the expected mean of 3.00 suggests that apprenticeship had a positive and significant effect on the succession planning of family-owned businesses. Furthermore, the hypothesis was equally subjected to double test using both Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient and Simple Linear Regression to appraise the effect of apprenticeship on the succession planning of family-owned businesses led to the rejection of null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternate hypothesis. Thus, the study concludes that a strong positive correlation exists between apprenticeship and succession planning in the South-East, Nigeria which is positive and significant ($r = 0.843$, $t = 38.249$, $F = 1302.769$ $p < 0.05$).

The above finding agrees with the study carried out by Adedayo, Kensinro and Fatunmbi (2017) who examined the effect of succession mentoring on sustainability of family-owned business in Lagos and Ogun States of Nigeria and found that succession mentoring (apprenticeship) significantly affected sustainability of family-owned business ($r = 0.777$; $p < 0.05$). The findings of this present study are also in agreement with several studies (Kuratko, Hornsby & Montago, 1993; Handler, 1990; Churchill & Hatten, 1987) that survival of family firms require proper mentoring (apprenticeship) of family members. Similar studies by Danco, (1982), Schein (1983), Hollander & Ellman (1988), Langsberg and Astrachan (1994), Langsberg (1999), Grote, (2003), Wang, Watkins, Harris and Spicer (2004), Le Breton-Miller et.al (2004), Chrisman, Chua, and Sharma, (2005) supported family members' commitment to the family business made manifest by the degree of their involvement in the business and the way they were integrated into the business and the fact that successor should have a clear idea of expectations and the process to be followed as communicated by the incumbent as well as the only way of making sure that the owner's knowledge gets passed on to the successor. Thus according to Adedayo, et al (2017), the new successor must be properly mentored, groomed and tutored on how to strike a balance between control, professionalism and human relations within the family business upon taking-over so as to retain and motivate the key managers in the family business. The findings also corroborate studies by Ogundele, Idris and Ahmed-Ogundipe, (2012) that mentoring the successor helps the firm's survival and sustainability. These findings further reinforce and make clear that early exposure of apprentices to the business allows them to become increasingly familiar with the business, its culture, values, and other members of the family as well as the opportunity to develop capabilities needed by the business to survive. In the words of Le Breton-Miller et.al (2004), 'mentoring begins at home in form of apprenticeship.'

Summary of Findings

The study made the following findings:

- i. That apprenticeship in the family business is undertaken as a strategy to ensure smooth leadership succession
- ii. That succession planning in family-owned businesses is based on the informal education, training and development of the future managers on the business.
- iii. That succession planning in most family-owned businesses is an effort at finding and breeding right people with skills, knowledge, attitudes, experience and behaviours within the family circle that can lead in the business.
- iv. That only successful apprenticeis considered during leadership succession in family-owned businesses.
- v. That apprenticeship benefits succession planning in family-owned businesses

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes based on the results above that apprenticeship positively and significantly benefits succession planning in a family-owned business, South-East, Nigeria. The study recommends that apprentices should be groomed, tested and held ready to succeed their masters when the need arises to save the businesses from succession crises which could lead to the death of the business.

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APPENDIX

Questionnaire

Instruction: The options to select are in the following scale. Please, indicate your opinion by shading below the number which matches your opinion in the table below:

5 = Strongly Agree (SA)

4 = Agree (A)

3 = Undecided (U)

2 = Disagree (D)

1 = Strongly Disagree (SD)

To examine the effect of apprenticeship on the succession planning in family-owned businesses					
Questions	SA	A	U	D	SD
a. Apprenticeship in the family business is undertaken as a strategy to ensure smooth leadership succession					
b. Succession planning in family-owned businesses is based on the informal education, training and development of the future managers on the business					
c. Succession planning in family-owned businesses is a deliberate effort within the family circle at finding and breeding right people with skills, knowledge, attitudes, experience and behaviours that are necessary to lead in the business					
d. Only successful apprentices are considered during leadership succession in family-owned businesses					
e. Apprenticeship does not benefit succession planning in family-owned businesses					

Table 1: Administration and Return of Questionnaire

Returned (R)	536	96.8	96.8	96.8
Valid Not Returned (NR)	18	3.2	3.2	100.0
Total	554	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 2: Abia State Questionnaire Administration and Return

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Returned (R)	137	95.1	95.1	95.1
Valid Not Returned (NR)	6	4.2	4.2	99.3
Not Properly Filled	1	.7	.7	100.0
Total	144	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 3: Anambra State Questionnaire Administration and Return

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Returned (R)	126	96.9	96.9	96.9
Valid Not Returned (NR)	3	2.3	2.3	99.2
Not Properly Filled	1	.8	.8	100.0
Total	130	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 4: Ebonyi State Questionnaire Administration and Return

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Returned (R)	93	98.9	98.9	98.9
Valid Not Returned (NR)	1	1.1	1.1	100.0
Total	94	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version

Table 5: Enugu State Questionnaire Administration and Return

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Returned (R)	83	97.6	97.6	97.6
Valid Not Returned (NR)	1	1.2	1.2	98.8
Not Properly Filled	1	1.2	1.2	100.0
Total	85	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 6: Imo State Questionnaire Administration and Return

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Returned (R)	97	96.0	96.0	96.0
Valid Not Returned (NR)	2	2.0	2.0	98.0
Not Properly Filled	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	101	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.